

**Co-Teaching in a Large Class in Higher Education
Working Collaboratively in Support of Engaging Pedagogy**

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Abstract

Cuseo (2007) identified eight potential negative outcomes in relation to student learning experience associated with large university classes. This paper uses Cuseo's hypothesis to frame the rationale for and presentation of the findings of a study wherein both authors co-taught a class of 400 students over four sessions using a workshop format. The findings suggest that the challenges outlined by Cuseo can be ameliorated if teaching strategies are considered in the co-taught context.

Keywords

Large Class, Higher Education, University, Co-teaching, Pedagogy

1. Introduction and Motivation

Large class size and plenary type lectures have been features of teaching and learning in higher education for many decades. However, the phenomenon of massification, a term used to describe the rapid increase in enrolment of students on many university programmes in recent decades (Hornsby & Osman, 2014) has placed the issue of class size firmly in the spotlight. This phenomenon can be partly explained by the imperative to increase access to and participation in tertiary education thus moving higher education from being considered an elite model to one of universal participation (Kerr, 2011). However, that change has occurred in the context of other demands (Kerr) including funding crises and reduction in the number of full-time faculty per full-time equivalent student.

For the most part, large class size is construed negatively, with an assumption that only a didactic, “information-transmission and teacher-focused” (Prosser & Trigwell, 2014, p. 791) pedagogical approach can be used in such contexts. Increasing class size appears to have a negative impact on student retention, particularly in first year where students may feel isolated in large classes (Moore-Cherry, Quin & Burroughs, 2015). Further, student engagement can be impacted negatively (Cuseo, 2007; Iaria & Hubbell, 2008) with students less actively involved in the learning process and experiencing lower levels of interaction with lecturers. Cuseo (2007) identified eight potential negative outcomes linked with large class size as outlined in Table 1.

	Outcome
1	increased faculty reliance on the <i>lecture</i> method of instruction
2	less <i>active student involvement</i> in the learning process
3	reduced frequency of instructor <i>interaction</i> with and <i>feedback</i> to students
4	reduced <i>depth of student thinking</i> inside the classroom
5	reduced breadth and depth of <i>course objectives</i> , <i>course assignments</i> , and course-related <i>learning strategies</i> used by students <i>outside</i> the classroom
6	lower levels of academic <i>achievement (learning)</i> and academic <i>performance (grades)</i>
7	reduced overall course <i>satisfaction</i> with the learning experience
8	<i>lower student ratings (evaluations)</i> of course instruction

Table 1 – Eight deleterious outcomes associated with large-sized classes (Cuseo, 2007, p. 2) (italics in original).

However, it is important to recognise that the effect of class size may be confounded by other variables such as teaching methods as well as a lack of conceptual clarity about what exactly constitutes a large class (Kerr, 2011). Moreover, it is very likely that student demographics, programme level and discipline may confound the effect of class size. Recently, assumptions that large classes are inherently problematic and impact negatively on teaching and learning have been questioned (Kerr, 2011) and there have been calls instead for a focus on the investigation of pedagogical approaches that support student learning within large classes (Hornsby & Osman, 2014; Teaching and Educational Development Institute, 2003), particularly in relation to the possibility of opportunities for collaborative group-work (Cooper and Robinson, 2000), thereby developing a classroom community (Iaria and Hubball, 2008).

Prosser & Trigwell (2014) question Cuseo's (2007) assertion that large class teaching is associated primarily with lecture type transmission 'talk at them' approaches. They assert that "students can be challenged to think deeply, critically and creatively in large classes" (p. 794), thereby mitigating the negative outcomes which Cuseo identified. Indeed, Hornsby and Osman (2014) go further asserting that the challenges associated with the large class context not only can be overcome when student learning is prioritised, but that large class contexts offer rich opportunities for research and innovation in teaching and learning.

In this paper we report on our experience of using co-teaching with a large class of 400 first year Bachelor of Education (BEd) students and consider the extent to which co-teaching might support higher education teachers in addressing the challenges and seizing the opportunities presented in large classes. Before reporting on this initiative it is necessary to consider what is meant by co-teaching in general and within higher education in particular.

Co-teaching is defined as 'two or more professionals delivering substantive instruction to a diverse, or blended, group of students in a single physical space' (Cook & Friend, 1995 p. 1). A feature of compulsory education for many years where it is typically associated with mainstream and special education teachers working together to support the inclusion of learners with learning difficulties or special educational needs (Friend, Cook, Hurley-Chamberlain & Shamberger, 2010), co-

teaching allows for a broader range of teaching strategies and differentiation for individual students where necessary (Carty & Farrell, 2018) and increasing inclusion of all students (Gately & Gately, 2001). To date, relatively little attention has been paid to co-teaching in higher education (Bacharach & Heck, 2007; Nevin, Thousand & Villa, 2009) where the concept appears to be understood variously as sharing the teaching on a module (Money & Coughlan, 2016), guest lecturing or even simply co-planning. In an analysis of co-teaching within initial teacher education programmes, Bacharach & Heck (2007) reported benefits for student learning and for faculty professional development. Students appreciated being exposed to the varied and often contrasting perspectives on concepts being taught and reported that the co-taught context was conducive to higher levels of classroom discussion and student-lecturer interaction.

This co-teaching initiative involved two lecturers jointly teaching the entire cohort together in 4 workshops in a tiered lecture theatre. The aim of the workshop series was to give students hands-on experience of problem-based tasks relating to a case study of the diagnostic assessment and individual education planning process. Each workshop was of 50 minutes duration and at various points involved direct teaching, students working in pairs and threes, and feedback to and from students and lecturers. In workshop 1 the student task involved the analysis of the pupil profile, in workshops 2 and 3 students analysed a range of assessments completed by the pupil to identify patterns of learning strengths and needs, and in workshop 4, students wrote SMART learning targets arising from the diagnostic assessment. All materials were made available on Moodle prior to the sessions and we also brought hard copies to the sessions. While feedback on student work was provided at the sessions, we also collected the tasks, analysed these and provided collective feedback afterwards on Moodle.

We met initially for about two hours to discuss the possibility of co-teaching this series of workshops; to clarify the content and sequence; and, to plan the roll-out over the sessions available. We liaised using google slides and docs to develop the materials to be used in the sessions. We met for approximately one hour before each workshop to plan each stage, refining how we would address the learning content and outcomes, and delineating our respective roles in relation to direct teaching input and

managing the learning activities. Every detail was carefully planned and meticulously timed. We agreed who would introduce and conclude the sessions, who would talk to each slide and for how long, when we would both circulate supporting students completing the workshop tasks, who would take feedback from students, and who would record this on screen. We also very deliberately built in opportunities where we could interject and meaningfully challenge each other in front of the students. Careful planning ensured that as co-teachers we were very clear about our roles although on occasion it was challenging to adhere to the agreed timings. However, it is notable that some students did experience the co-teaching as confusing; reflecting the findings of other studies (Bacharach & Heck, 2007; Stang & Lyons, 2008).

2. Methodology

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of co-teaching as a pedagogic approach within a large class context. As such our starting point and purpose reflects an action research approach with a focus on improvement across three dimensions namely; our practice, our understanding of our practice and our professional situation (Robson, 2011). Moreover, the substantive focus on our professional collaboration coupled with our intention to seek the perspectives of colleagues and our students illustrates our concern with the emancipatory purpose of action research through involvement. While data collection methods such as participant reflections and unstructured observations typically associated with qualitative, naturalistic inquiry were appropriate, survey methods were the only feasible method to elicit the student perspective.

At the time of this research, the authors were working together as teacher educators in a university faculty of education. The research took place with two consecutive cohorts of 400 BEd 1 students who completed an anonymous end of module evaluation which included a number of questions pertaining to the co-taught workshops. In year two we asked two university colleagues to each observe and give us feedback on one co-taught workshop. Both peer observers provided written and oral feedback. Two co-taught sessions in year two were video-recorded and analysed to supplement and inform our reflective notes written after each session. The study

was approved by the institutional research ethics committee. All questionnaires were anonymous and included a plain language statement outlining the nature and purpose of the study. Video was recorded from the back of the lecture theatre and was viewed only by the authors.

3. Findings and Discussion

The report and discussion of the findings regarding the effectiveness of co-teaching in the large class are framed in relation to each of the conclusions about the negative outcomes of large classes presented in Cuseo (2007) and listed in Table 1. Before addressing outcomes 2 to 8, it is important to first consider Cuseo's first conclusion namely that large classes are associated with increase in the extent to which faculty rely "on the lecture method of instruction" (p.2). Internationally, increasing attention is being paid to pedagogical approaches in large classes (Kerr, 2011; Teaching and Educational Development Institute, 2003) and there is evidence of higher education teachers adapting a diverse range of active teaching approaches in large classes (Hornby & Osman, 2014; Prosser & Trigwell; Clarence, Albertus & Mwambene 2014). It seems reasonable to conclude that this reflects a recognition of the critical importance of large class teaching "one of the most tangible and clear impacts of massification which presents conceptual challenges that require...adapting teaching practices" (Hornsby & Osman, p.717). Arguably this refutes, to some extent, Cuseo's first conclusion.

The second negative outcome identified by Cuseo (2007) is that in large classes students have less active involvement in learning. Evidence from student survey responses and from fieldnotes recorded by both peer observers suggest that co-teaching enabled the kind of active involvement that might not otherwise be possible in the large class context. Students reported that

Co-teaching was very effective. I felt I learned a lot more in the workshops than I did in the normal lectures because we were more involved (Respondent (R)111)... It can help those who may find it difficult to listen to one lecturer reading lecture content... it is a more interactive and hands-on way to engage

with the course concepts (R5).., It was very helpful as we did not just sit and listen to the lecturers, we actively participated (R13)

Peer observer 1 also noted good levels of active involvement.

The two of you set off around the lecture theatre. I can hear students close to me – initial question from one about whether they need to write something, but they're mostly on topic. In your instructions, I liked the focus of the task; the requirement to discuss with a partner (good peer learning and social constructivism here); the knowledge in advance that some will be called upon to share in public; and the assured anonymity of any examples posted on Moodle.

In relation to conclusion 3, namely that large classes are associated with a reduction in lecturer interaction and feedback to students; the findings indicate that the co-taught workshops facilitated interaction and feedback between lecturers and students.

It was very helpful as you felt more motivated to contribute ideas and discuss them with people round you (R126)...It made the lecture more interesting as we weren't just staring and listening to one person at the bottom talking. It also allowed us to actively join in and take part (R162).

Also noteworthy is that a student recognised the value of co-teaching in terms of lecturers formatively assessing student learning. *With two lecturers a closer eye can be kept on how the students are understanding the concept being taught (R39).*

The peer observers also identified the high levels of engagement and interaction.

Observer 2 noted

It is hard to see how you'd effectively accomplish this task without there being two of you. It's a large group; one of you is on each aisle, and you seem to be engaging fairly constantly. If this help was not available, I think some students might be held up...The way you are managing this feedback process is pretty effective. Students are getting oral instruction on how to improve the targets, alongside seeing these amended on screen by (Author 1) as (Author 2) talks.

Cuseo's fourth conclusion is that levels of deep thinking are lower in large classes. Survey responses seem to suggest that at least some students engaged in deep thinking during the workshops.

[Co-teaching] encouraged me to think more about what we were doing in the lectures and allowed me to put my teacher hat on for the duration of the

lecture to think about how I would best help a child with special educational needs (R5). I found it easier to understand when we are taking part in the workshops than just listening to the notes (R81).

Cuseo's fifth and sixth conclusions concern the potential negative impact on student learning of large class teaching beyond the confines of the large class context itself in terms of learning outcomes, assessment, achievement and grades. The data from this study relate only to the co-taught workshops and so do not shed light on student engagement beyond the large class context. Nevertheless, our analysis of the tasks completed by students during and after the workshops gave us insight into their understanding and enabled us to provide students with feedback on their work. This we hoped would ultimately scaffold their learning in preparation for summative assessment of the module which required them to engage in and to demonstrate their skills and ability in solving similar problem-based tasks to those presented in the co-taught workshops.

Cuseo's final two conclusions relate to student satisfaction with and evaluation of the learning and the teaching they experience in large classes. Overall, student responses indicate a high level of satisfaction with co-teaching.

It is another effective way in which information can be passed on and it also a way which captured my attention and the attention of other students because it was a practical type of session and although we were being provided with a lot of information, it was taught in a way which allowed us to process it easily (R170) Very effective...Putting up the notes on Moodle is a good idea as it saves us writing lots of notes, therefore we are able to listen to the lecturers more actively (R85)...Co-teaching is very helpful because while one moves around the hall and interacts with us (picking up our written words is very subtle and therefore very helpful) while the other will be speaking to us from the bottom of the hall and communicating to us in the traditional sense. It's best of both worlds as you get the informative lecture plus a slightly more one to one atmosphere and familiarity even in a massive hall (R79).

However, it is important to note that some students were less satisfied with co-taught sessions and reported negative impacts on their learning finding the presence of two lecturers distracting and experiencing the co-taught sessions as confusing. One student described co-teaching as “an interrupted way to teach” (R156), while another noted that “It was difficult to learn from both lecturers at the same time” (R146). The

following response sheds some light on this with a student noting “I found it difficult to engage in the lessons as the co-operating teachers jumped from one person to another at various stages and I found it difficult to concentrate on who was speaking” (R17). In year 1 in particular, some students also perceived inequalities between the co-teachers observing that one teacher seemed to dominate “I felt one was speaking more or teaching more than the other” (R84) or “one [lecturer] tried to be in control in the lecture, even though it was co-taught” (R139). The issue of role equality in co-teaching is among the challenges identified in research about co-teaching in compulsory schooling and could be explored with student teachers in subsequent deconstruction of co-teaching. The confusion experienced by some students in co-taught lectures arguably reflects students’ perceptions and prior experiences of large class teaching in higher education. Nevertheless, the potential for confusion warrants consideration by other researchers who might wish to explore the potential of co-teaching in large classes across other disciplines.

4. Conclusions and Future Work

In this paper we have drawn on the findings emerging from this small-scale practitioner research study investigating the effectiveness of co-teaching as a pedagogic approach within a large class context. As such, our focus was on improvement of our practice as teacher educators, our understanding of co-teaching and of the large class context (Robson, 2011). Framing the presentation and analysis in terms of Cuseo’s (2007) typology of challenges associated with large class size, we conclude that these may be somewhat ameliorated in co-taught contexts. However, notwithstanding the generally very positive feedback from students and peer observers, it is important to acknowledge that a minority of students found the co-taught lectures to be less effective.

I felt that I didn't really benefit from the co-teaching lessons. There was nothing wrong with both lecturers. Both were very formative, friendly and approachable. However I felt there was no need for two lecturers. I felt myself distracted focusing on the lecturers jumping from person to person instead of focusing on the content of the actual lecture (R32).

While we are not suggesting that large classes are ideal for teaching and learning, we hope that this research may serve to illustrate the potential of co-teaching as one of many pedagogical approaches which have potential utility for higher education

teachers working with large classes. Arguably the challenges of the large class can best be recognised and overcome when faculty adopt a ‘student focused’ approach (Prosser & Trigwell, 2014). Thus, as recommended by Hornsby and Osman (2014) we intend in future studies to build on this initiative by seeking the perspective of students on what supports and impedes their learning in large classes. This might shed further light on how the confusion experienced by some students in co-taught lectures could be ameliorated. It is by working collaboratively with each other and with our students that we can better understand the dynamics of engaging pedagogy whether in large or in small teaching and learning contexts.

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